

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF SODIUM CHLORIDE (NaCl) ON THE VEGETATIVE GROWTH OF THREE VARIETIES OF COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* L.)

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Abstract

In this study effect of different concentrations of Sodium Chloride (NaCl) on the vegetative growth of cowpea (*Vigna* sp.) varieties (Ife-brown, IT90K-82 and IAR-48) were studied. The experiment was arranged in a complete randomized design in the biological garden of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. Sodium chloride was applied to the plants at 10, 20 and 30g/l. The shoot growth of cowpea varieties were inhibited by salt stress. NaCl significantly decreased leaf production, leaf number and leaf area. The result showed that in all the varieties of plants studied, as the concentration of NaCl increases, there was progressive reduction in the parameters measured. Among the cowpea varieties studied, IAR-48 was the most sensitive to salt treatment while Ife-brown showed better results followed by IT90K-82 in respect to salt tolerance.

INTRODUCTION

Salinity is the saltiness or dissolved salt content of a body of water. It is a general term used to describe the levels of different salts such as sodium chloride, magnesium and calcium sulfates, and bicarbonates (World Ocean Atlas 2005). Salinity is an ecological factor of considerable importance influencing the kinds of plants that will grow either in a water body, or on land fed by water or by a ground water (Kalcic *et al.*, 2011). Soil salinity is the salt content in the soil. Increasing salinity is one of the most significant environmental problems facing the world especially the tropics.

Salinity and drought are the two major environmental factors that currently reduce plant productivity (Serrano *et al.*, 1999), and these stresses cause similar reactions in plants due to water stress. These environmental concerns affect plants more than is commonly thought. For example, the effect of disease and insect typically decrease crop yields by less than ten percent, but abiotic stresses, such as drought, salinity, extreme temperatures, chemical toxicity and oxidative stress are serious threats to agriculture and result in the deterioration of the environment. Abiotic stress is the primary cause of crop loss worldwide, reducing average yields for most major crop plants by more than 50% (Boyer, 1982). One of the most important abiotic factors limiting plant germination and early seedling stages is water stress brought about by drought and salinity (Almomsouri, Kinet and Lutts 2001), which are widespread problems around the world.

There are global constraints on fresh water supplies, and this has led to a surge of interest in reusing water (Shannon and Grieve, 1999). However, in many cases the value of water has decreased because the water is salty. There is evidence that irrigation systems and type of irrigation water have contributed to a large extent in converting arable lands to saline lands (Ashraf and McNeilly, 2004). Hence, salt stress can be a major challenge to plants. It limits agriculture all over the world, particularly on irrigated farmlands (Rausch, 1996).

Salinity, due to over-accumulation of NaCl, is usually of great concern and the most injurious factor in arid and semi arid regions. Despite the essentiality of chloride as a micronutrient for all higher plants and of sodium as mineral nutrient for many halophytes, salt accumulation may convert agricultural areas in to unfavorable environments, reduce local biodiversity, limit growth and reproduction of plants and may lead to toxicity in non salt-tolerant plants, known as glycophytes (Marschner, 1995). Most of the cultivated plants are sensitive to salt stress, in which NaCl - salinity causes reduction in vegetative growth, the rate of photosynthesis (Erdal *et al.*, 2000, Neto *et al.*, 2004) and also water availability and imbalance in nutrient uptake by plants (Pessaraki and Tucker, 1988).

Salinity is one of the most important abiotic stress factors limiting plant growth and productivity (Khan and Panda, 2008). Salinity affects almost every aspect of the physiology and biochemistry of plants and significantly reduces yield. High exogenous salt concentrations affect seed germination, water deficit, cause ion imbalance of the cellular ions resulting in ion toxicity and osmotic stress (Khan *et al.*, 2002; Khan and Panda, 2008).

The ability of plants to survive and maintain their growth under saline conditions is known as salt tolerance. This is a variable trait that is dependent on many factors, including the species of the plant, genotype, plant age, ionic strength and composition of the saline solution, and the organ in question. Plants are classified based on tolerance to saline conditions into glycophytes that are sensitive to salt, and halophytes which survive in very high concentrations of salt (Volkmar *et al.*, 1998).

Characters like yield, survival, vigor, leaf damage and plant height, have been the most commonly used criteria for identifying salinity tolerance (Shannon, 1984).

Cowpea belongs to leguminous plant with edible seeds contained in long, narrow and dehiscent pods that developed from pundles (Arthur, 2009). According to Henshaw (2008), Nigeria is the largest producer of cowpea. It completes its life cycle within a season, making it to be an annual crop. It exhibits various growth habit such as erect, twining, climbing, semi-erect and prostrate depending on the species. The leaves are alternate, trifoliate usually green in colour but brown when dry and the leaflets are ovate shaped and large.

Cowpea serves as a major cheap and efficient source of needed protein to balance human diet in tropics particularly Nigeria. In which the foods are mainly made up of cereals, roots and tubers.

Cowpea has a number of common names, including crowder pea, blackeyed pea, southern pea, and internationally as lubia, niebe, coupe or frijole. However, they are all the species *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp, which in older references may be identified as *Vigna sinensis* (L.). The largest acreage is in Africa, with Nigeria and Niger predominating, but Brazil, West Indies, India, United States, Burma, Sri

Lanka, Yugoslavia, and Australia all have significant production. Dry seed production is estimated at 1.24 million tons annually.

Cowpea is an important food legume, and its use as a leafy vegetable is essential in many African countries. Cowpea has become a cover crop of some interest as it may be suitable for growth during summer months in desert valleys when vegetables are not usually grown because it is adapted to high temperatures and drought (Ehlers, 1997 and Hall; 1985). The optimum temperature requirement is between 20 degree and 35 degree centigrade during its life cycle (Sign *et al.*, 2003). Drought tolerance, short growing period and its multi-purpose use make cowpea a very attractive alternative for farmers who cultivate in marginal, drought-prone areas with low rainfall and less developed irrigation systems, where infrastructure, food security and diminishing malnutrition are major challenges.

However, despite its regional importance, cowpea's use as leafy vegetable in many African countries has been widely neglected in research and improvement programs (Barrett, 1990; Schippers, 2002), and it can, therefore, be considered as a neglected crop. Although lately, some research has been carried out on African indigenous vegetables, especially leafy ones, cowpea research continued to focus on improvements of the grain and/or the entire herbage for animal feed (Singh *et al.*, 2003). Yet it is the leaves of some legumes, like cowpea, that show much promise for producing part of the vastly increased supplies of nutrients that the world population needs. Therefore, the need remains to further intensively research and promote leafy vegetables and their benefits to show the importance of their use. Hence, Wilson *et al.*, 2006, concluded that salt tolerance in cowpea is mainly concerned with leaf area and dry weight such that the leaves might be likely targets for investigation. In addition to reducing lateral branch emergence, salt-stressed cowpea plants produced proportionally more leaves than stems and roots, (Claudivan, 2006).

The cowpea varieties studied here are Ife-brown, IT90K-82 and IAR-48 and are of the following characteristics; the seed sizes of the three varieties are medium. They have rough seed coat. Ife-brown and IT90K-82 are brown in colour while IAR-

48 is white. The growth habit for Ife-brown is semi erect while others are erect. The maturity days are 60 for Ife-brown and IT90K-82 and 75 for IAR-48. Other qualities are; Ife brown and IAR-48 have high yield and IT90K-82 is moderately resistant to insect, pest and diseases.

This study was carried out to determine the tolerance of these three cowpea varieties to salt stress which can be grown on cultivated lands having high salt content.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Biological garden of Department of biology, Kwara state College of Education Ilorin during the months of January to April 2012. Three varieties (IT90K-82, IFE-BROWN and IAR-48) of cowpea were used. The seeds were tested for viability by carrying out germination test in the Biology laboratory at Kwara State College of Education Ilorin.

The emergence of plumule was taken as index of germination. Initiation and completion of germination was recorded daily. The germination percentage was recorded for 10 days and germination percentage was calculated with the following formula: Germination percentage (%) = Number of germinated seeds / total number of seeds x 100.

Ten seeds of each cowpea varieties were sown into each 4L plastic pot containing 3000g of sandy-loamy soil. The seeds were sown 2.5cm deep and 4cm apart. Immediately after sowing, soils were watered with 250ml and watering was carried out regularly every day till the commencements of salt stress. The plants were later thinned to six in a pot after emergence.

Germination of seedling were observed for cowpea varieties as thus, Ife brown germinated three days after planting, IT90K-82 and IAR-48 germinated four days after planting.

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at (p<0.05).

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Pots were arranged in four rows, each row represents a condition of treatment with treatment control. Each condition of salt treatment consists of three replicates which sum up to twelve pots in each variety making a total of thirty-six pots.

For salinity treatments, non-salt-treated plants were kept as controls and salt stressed plants were subjected to 10, 20 and 30g/l NaCl throughout the experimental period. The salinity treatments started two weeks after planting and were maintained till the end of experiment i.e ninth week after planting.

Salt treatments were prepared by dissolving separately calculated amounts of NaCl in water and kept in 25l jerry can. Plants were irrigated daily with 250ml solution of the respective treatment standardized using a measuring cylinder of 250ml capacity. Data collection commenced at the second week of planting when the following growth parameters were determined; plant height, number of leaves, leaf length (cm), leaf breadth (cm), and leaf area (cm²) on weekly basis.

Leaf area was determined according to the formula by Noyt and Bradfield, 1962 as follows:

Leaf area=Leaf length × Leaf breadth ×0.75 i.e correction factor. The means of leaf length and leaf breadth were used.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The experimental design was a randomized complete block design with four treatments and three replications. Data were subjected to statistical analysis using ANOVA, a statistical package available from SPSS17. Significant differences between treatments were determined using Duncan's Multiple Range test at the 0.05 level.

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RESULTS

Effect of different NaCl concentration on the stem height of cowpea varieties

The result as shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3 revealed that at the initial two weeks of planting the growth were virtually similar across all the treatments. The control plants had the highest stem height all through the planting period in all the varieties of the plant, a decrease in stem height was noticed in other treated plants with increasing NaCl concentration in the soil. This means that a high NaCl application has adverse effect on these cowpea varieties.

Table 1: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on stem height (cm) of cowpea Ife-brown

Treatment(g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	12.70a	17.7a	20.17a	36.06a	41.46a	47.76a	52.00a	63.90a
10	11.80a	14.45b	16.27b	23.90b	26.08b	30.28b	32.65b	35.44b
20	11.61ab	12.41c	14.31c	18.01c	20.60c	23.03c	26.06c	28.00c
30	10.00b	12.09c	14.70bc	16.06c	18.03c	20.03c	21.5d	21.10d

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at (p<0.05).

Table 2: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on stem height (cm) of cowpea IT90K-82

Treatment (g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	14.71a	17.87a	25.33a	33.27a	39.28a	46.80a	50.81a	59.57a
10	13.01ab	15.53ab	20.03b	26.07b	29.1b	34.63b	38.50ab	42.44a
20	12.09b	14.93b	17.4bc	23.50bc	27.53bc	30.80b	32.07bc	34.03c
30	10.15c	12.00c	15.67c	18.03c	22.43c	23.93c	24.4c	24.47d

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at (p<0.05).

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Table 3: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on stem height (cm) of cowpea IAR-48

Treatment (g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	14.36a	19.93a	25.93a	32.13a	40.66a	47.47a	56.10a	62.85a
10	10.40b	14.96b	17.90b	22.50b	27.56b	30.36b	34.43b	38.47b
20	10.00b	12.40bc	15.73bc	18.00b	22.56bc	24.36bc	27.54bc	30.98b
30	9.34b	11.36c	14.70c	17.67b	18.10c	19.68c	22.40c	20.61c

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of different NaCl concentration on Leaf Morphology

Tables 4, 5 and 6 shown that, varying concentration of NaCl produced significant effect on the leaf production at each growth stage. There is also significant difference in terms of leaf production among the plants varieties studied. IT90K-82 and Ife-brown had no remarkable variation as observed in the number of leaf produced until six weeks after planting (6WAP). At this stage, change in the greenness of leaf colour and leaf defoliation was observed. However, chlorosis was first noticed in IAR-48 variety. These effects were pronounced in the plants treated with NaCl concentration of 20g/l and 30g/l. It was also observed that lower leaves were more affected.

30	10.13a	13.90a	17.03a	22.43a	24.47a
20	13.09a	14.93a	17.49a	23.20a	24.03a
10	13.01a	12.32a	20.02a	26.07a	29.11a
Control	13.01a	14.83a	18.80a	23.80a	28.44a

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at ($p > 0.05$).

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Table 4: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on Number of leaf of cowpea Ife-brown

Treatment (g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	8.00a	9.00a	15.00a	17.00a	19.00a	25.00a	28.00a	32.00a
10	8.00a	8.00a	14.00a	14.00a	16.00a	20.00b	19.00b	16.00b
20	5.00b	8.00a	12.00a	13.00a	15.00a	16.00bc	16.00bc	12.00bc
30	8.00a	9.00a	14.70a	13.00a	15.00a	13.00c	12.00c	10.00c

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on Number of leaf of cowpea IT90K-82

Treatment (g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	8.00a	11.00a	16.30a	21.00a	23.00a	29.00a	32.70a	35.50a
10	7.00a	8.00a	11.30b	17.70a	19.00a	21.00b	19.70b	19.5b
20	6.00a	8.00a	10.70b	12.70b	17.00a	18.30b	15.30b	14.24b
30	7.00a	8.00a	8.00b	12.00b	16.00a	14.30b	14.00b	13.66b

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$).

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Table 6: Effect of salt (NaCl) concentration on Number of leaf of cowpea IAR-48

Treatment(g/l)	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	7WAP	8WAP	9WAP
Control	9.00d	11.00a	17.00a	20.00a	24.33a	32.00a	35.00a	37.00a
10	7.00c	9.00a	14.00ab	14.00b	18.00b	20.00b	21.00b	19.00b
20	5.00b	8.00a	12.00bc	12.00b	13.67bc	18.00bc	18.00bc	16.00b
30	8.00a	8.00a	10.00c	11.00b	13.00c	14.00c	14.00c	14.00b

Values bearing the same letter(s) along the same column are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of different NaCl concentration on Leaf Area of cowpea varieties

Salinity stress produced significant effect on the leaf area in cowpea varieties studied. At three weeks after planting (3WAP), there was no significant effect in both the control and treated plants. The reason for this may be because they had just been exposed to salinity condition. However, as depicted in figures 1, 2 & 3, from 4WAP there was significant difference in leaf area in the salt treated plants. A higher reduction in leaf area was observed in IAR-48 when compared to the two other varieties. This result shows that on the average the control group (non-saline) had highest leaf area all through the period of planting. This is undoubtedly a function of the larger available area for photosynthesis.

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Fig 1: Effect of salinity stress on the leaf area (cm²) of cowpea Iife-Brown

Fig 2: Effect of salinity stress on the leaf area (cm²) of cowpea II90K-82

Fig 3: Effect of salinity stress on the leaf area (cm²) of cowpea IAR-48

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The effect of increasing concentration of NaCl on the shoot height was not significant for the three varieties of cowpea at the initial two weeks of treatment application but became significant at 6 weeks after planting to 9 weeks after planting (WAP). For the three varieties of cowpea studied, the first marked effect of toxic-level NaCl for 20 & 30g/l dosages was a reduction in the green parts (stem and leaves) and a decrease in the growth rate of the plants. According to result of analysis of variance, plant height was influenced significantly by the salt stress ($P < 0.05$). The effect of 30g/l NaCl treatment leads to a marked reduction in the plant height of the three varieties as compared to control (non saline). Thus, plant growth was reduced by rising NaCl concentration in cowpea plant.

In general, salt stress affected negatively the plant height, but the effect differs among the varieties. The significant level (reduction) was very high in IAR-48 variety of cowpea.

Salinity stress results not only in inhibition of shoot height but also on leaf number. The results of the analysis of variance for the leaf production at different growth stages showed that an increasing salinity stress produced significant effect on the leaf production at each growth stage. This study revealed a significant reduction in leaf number with rising salinity and it was marked from the fourth week of treatment. This was recorded in the three varieties of cowpea studied. The varieties also differed significantly in the areas of leaf production. The leaf production was lowest in IAR-48 and followed by IT90K-82 varieties. Similar finding has been observed for other plant species (Bernstein *et al.*, 1993; Lacerda *et al.*, 2003). The process of leaf growth inhibition can be associated with osmotic and toxic effects of salt stress (Munns, 2002).

The experiment showed that salinity stress had adverse effect on the leaf area of all the treated plants. There was a reduction in the leaf area expansion observed at the onset of treatment. It was observed that on the average, the control (non saline) had the highest leaf area in throughout the experimental period. This was followed by those treated with low level of NaCl (10g/l). Plants in control experiment did better

since they had highest leaf area for photosynthesis leading to higher nutrition uptake. These results revealed responses of leaf expansion to salt stress, which has been mainly associated with the osmotic component of salt stress and adjustment of leaf to the water available (Munns, 2002).

CONCLUSION

This study showed that the trend in the parameters obtained for unstressed plants (control) followed the normal and expected pattern but deviated in the other stressed plants. The control treatment achieved the highest values of shoot heights in the three varieties of cowpea plants as well as number of leaves and leaf area. Thus, increasing salt concentration from this study's outcome can cause reduction in plant growth, yield and even death. These adverse effects of salinity may be a consequence of water stress (and consequently drought stress), ion toxicities, ion imbalance, or a combination of all these factors.

Among these cowpea varieties, Ife-brown tolerated salt better than two other varieties. Hence, there is need for determination of the salt content of arable land and fertilizers by farmers in order to enhance productivity.

However, to evaluate physiological and morphological responses of bean varieties to salinity stress, further studies may be needed for screening bean for salinity tolerance. These may include physiological markers such as shoot and root fresh weight, dry weight, relative growth rate and photosynthesis rate as essential parameters for screening for salinity.

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